

Fractional Newton-Type Inequalities for Twice Differentiable Convex Functions Using Riemann-Liouville Integrals

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Abstract

In this study, Newton-type inequalities for twice differentiable convex functions, including Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals are established. Firstly, an identity involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integral is derived, which is then used to obtain new Newton-type inequalities. These inequalities are derived by utilizing the convexity of twice differentiable functions, Hölder's inequality, and the power mean inequality. The results are further illustrated through special cases of the derived theorems.

1. Introduction

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule forms the cornerstone of Simpson's second rule. Estimated results of three-step quadratic kernels are usually described as Newton-type results. The literature refers to these results as Newton-type inequalities. Many mathematicians have studied Newton-type inequalities. For instance, Gao and Shi presented Newton-type inequalities for twice-differentiable functions in [13]. In [24] and [23], the authors established Newton-type inequalities for p -harmonic convex functions and harmonic convex functions. Luangboon et al. derived some Newton-type inequalities using post-quantum integrals in [20]. Moreover, Ali et al. introduced quantum differentiable convex functions with Newton-type inequalities in [1]. Furthermore, Erden et al. obtained Newton-type quadrature formulas using Lipschitzian mappings and bounded variation, providing error estimates in [10]. See the references in [9, 18, 22] for additional recent advances on Newton-type inequalities.

Due to its numerous applications across various scientific fields, interest in fractional calculus has surged recently. Several operators for fractional integrals have been considered, given the significance of fractional calculus. For example, Erden et al. derived Newton-type inequalities for functions whose first derivatives, raised to a given power in absolute value, are arithmetically-harmonically convex in

[11]. Additionally, in [27], the authors presented Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation and Newton-type inequalities involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions. Moreover, Hezenci et al. established several Newton-type inequalities based on Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions in [15]. For more information, refer to [3, 7, 8, 14, 16, 17, 28, 29].

In the scientific literature, differentiable functions play a crucial role. Studies on twice-differentiable functions have been significantly advanced by the efforts of numerous mathematicians. Hadamard-type inequalities have been obtained in [4] and [5] using twice-differentiable convex functions. Furthermore, Mohammed and Sar?kaya established various generalized fractional integral inequalities of trapezoid-type and midpoint-type based on twice-differentiable convex mappings in [21]. Sarikaya and Aktan obtained new Simpson and Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for mappings whose second derivatives were considered in [26]. Budak et al. presented midpoint- and trapezoid-type inequalities for mappings with convex second derivatives in modulus, using generalized fractional integrals in [6]. Additionally, in [13], Gao and Shi proved novel Newton-type inequalities based on twice-differentiable convex functions.

The introduction and preliminaries are the first two sections of the paper's structure. The essential definitions of fractional calculus are given in Section 2, along with a

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discussion of recent research in the field. To obtain the main conclusions, an integral identity is proved in Section 3. Section 4 utilizes Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals to obtain fractional Newton-type inequalities for twice differentiable convex functions. We conclude by offering our opinions on Newton-type inequalities and talking about how they might affect future lines of research in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

Simpson-type inequality is a variant of the inequality derived from Simpson’s rule. It can be formulated as follows:

- Simpson’s $\frac{1}{3}$ rule, otherwise known as Simpson’s quadrature formula:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

- Simpson’s second formula, also referred to as the Simpson’s $\frac{3}{8}$ rule or the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

The three-point Simpson-type inequality is the most widely applied Newton-Cotes quadrature, and it is expressed as:

Theorem 1. Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function that is four times differentiable and continuous on (a, b) , and assume that $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality is satisfied:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

The Simpson’s $\frac{3}{8}$ rule, a classical closed quadrature method, is given as follows:

Theorem 2. Consider that $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable, continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Definition 1. (See, [25]) Let I be an interval of real numbers. A function $f \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called convex if, for all $x, y \in I$ and for all $t \in [0,1]$, the following inequality holds:

$$f(tx + (1-t)y) \leq tf(x) + (1-t)f(y).$$

Definition 2. (See, [12], [19]). Let us consider $f \in L_1[a, b]$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \tag{1}$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \tag{2}$$

respectively. Here, Γ denotes the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

3. A Significant Identity

In this section, we derive an integral equality to establish the main results of this paper.

Lemma 1. If $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) such that $f'' \in L_1[a, b]$, then the identity

$$\frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] = \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} [I_1 + I_2]$$

is valid. Here,

$$I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right) \left[f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt,$$

$$I_2 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right) \left[f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt.$$

Proof. By applying integration by parts, one can obtain the following identity:

$$I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right) \left[f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt$$

$$= \frac{2}{b-a} \left(t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right) \left[f' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) - f' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] \Big|_0^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$- \frac{2}{b-a} \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left((\alpha+1)t^\alpha - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) \right) \left[f' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt$$

$$= \frac{2}{b-a} \left(\left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) \right) \left[f' \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) - f' \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$- \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\frac{2}{b-a} (\alpha+1)t^\alpha - \frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right] \left[f \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] \Big|_0^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$- \frac{2\alpha(\alpha+1)}{b-a} \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\alpha-1} \left[f \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) \right] dt$$

$$= \frac{2}{b-a} \left(\left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) \right) \left[f' \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) - f' \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$- \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^2 \left((\alpha+1) \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^\alpha - \frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) \left[f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$+ \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^2 \frac{\alpha+1}{4} (f(a) + f(b))$$

$$+ \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^2 \alpha(\alpha+1) \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\alpha-1} \left[f \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt.$$

Likewise, one can immediately obtain

$$I_2 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right) \left[f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f'' \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt$$

$$= -\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{2(\alpha+1)}{3} + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right) \left[f' \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + f' \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$+ \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^2 \left(\left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^\alpha (\alpha+1) - (\alpha+1) \right) \left[f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$- \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^2 \alpha(\alpha+1) \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t^{\alpha-1} \left[f \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt.$$

If (3) is added to (4) and multiplied by $\frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)}$, then we have

$$\frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} [I_1 + I_2]$$

$$= \frac{\alpha}{2} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} \left[f \left(\frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a \right) + f \left(\frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b \right) \right] dt$$

$$- \frac{3}{8} \left[f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{8} [f(a) + f(b)].$$

Let us apply the variable change $x = \frac{t}{2} b + \frac{2-t}{2} a$ and $y = \frac{t}{2} a + \frac{2-t}{2} b$ for $t \in [0,1]$. With this substitution, the equality (5) can be reformulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} [I_1 + I_2] \\ &= \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \\ & - \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Then the proof of Lemma 1 is completed.

4. Fractional Newton-type inequalities by twice differentiable convex functions

In this section, we derive Newton-type inequalities for twice-differentiable convex functions using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals.

Theorem 3. Let the conditions of Lemma 1 be satisfied, and suppose that the function $|f''|$ is convex on the interval $[a, b]$. Then, the following fractional Newton-type inequality can be established:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} (\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha)) [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Here,

$$\Omega_1(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t \right| dt$$

and

$$\Omega_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt. \tag{8}$$

Proof. Let us begin by using the absolute value in Lemma 1. From this, we can immediately derive the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t \right| |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right)| \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right)| \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Based on the convexity of $|f''|$, we obtain the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(b)| \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)| + \frac{t}{2} |f''(a)| \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)| \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(b)| \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)| + \frac{t}{2} |f''(a)| \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)| \right] dt \right\} \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} (\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha)) [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. By setting $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3, one can derive a Newton-type inequality for twice-differentiable convex functions

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{384} [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

which is proved by Gao and Shi in [13].

Theorem 4. Assume the conditions of Lemma 1 hold, and the function $|f''|^q$, with $q > 1$, is convex on $[a, b]$. Then, Newton-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\frac{|f''(b)|^q + 5|f''(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\frac{5|f''(b)|^q + 7|f''(a)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{5|f''(a)|^q + 7|f''(b)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

is valid. Here, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Proof. By using Hölder's inequality in (9), one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |t^{\alpha+1} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b\right) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2}a \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a\right) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b\right) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2}a \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a\right) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left. \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

From the convexity of $|f''|^q$, one can readily derive

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f''(b)|^q + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f''(a)|^q + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f''(b)|^q + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f''(a)|^q + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &= \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4}\right)t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left[\left(\frac{|f''(b)|^q + 5|f''(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ &\quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} t^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left[\left(\frac{|f''(b)|^q + 5|f''(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\times \left[\left(\frac{5|f''(b)|^q + 7|f''(a)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{5|f''(a)|^q + 7|f''(b)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1. Consider setting $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4. Then, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{16} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} |t^2 - \frac{t}{2}|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\frac{|f''(b)|^q + 5|f''(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\ &\quad + \left. \left(\frac{1}{2p+1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{2p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\frac{5|f''(b)|^q + 7|f''(a)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|f''(a)|^q + 7|f''(b)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Theorem 5. If the assumptions of Lemma 1 hold and the function $|f''|^q$, $q \geq 1$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then the following Newton-type inequality satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\Omega_3(\alpha) |f''(b)|^q + \Omega_4(\alpha) |f''(a)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + [\Omega_3(\alpha)|f''(a)|^q + \Omega_4(\alpha)|f''(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\Omega_5(\alpha)|f''(b)|^q + \Omega_6(\alpha)|f''(a)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + [\Omega_5(\alpha)|f''(a)|^q + \Omega_6(\alpha)|f''(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \Big\},
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Omega_1(\alpha)$ and $\Omega_2(\alpha)$ are given in Theorem 3 and

$$\Omega_3(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{t}{2} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt,$$

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{2-t}{2} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt,$$

$$\Omega_5(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \frac{t}{2} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt,$$

and

$$\Omega_6(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \frac{2-t}{2} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt.$$

Proof. By first applying (9) to the power-mean inequality, we derive

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| \left| f''\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Big\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

It is known that $|f''|^q$ is convex. Then, one can establish

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(b)|^q \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha+1} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. - \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{4} \right) t \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(a)|^q \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(b)|^q \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \times \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^{\alpha+1} - (\alpha+1)t + \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \right| \left[\frac{t}{2} |f''(a)|^q \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \frac{2-t}{2} |f''(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\}. \end{aligned}$$

After the necessary calculations, the proof is completed.

Corollary 2. If we take $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 5, then the following Newton-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{1296} \left\{ \frac{19^{1-\frac{1}{q}}}{8} \left[\left(\frac{27|f''(b)|^q + 125|f''(a)|^q}{8} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{27|f''(a)|^q + 125|f''(b)|^q}{8} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left[\left(\frac{3|f''(b)|^q + 5|f''(a)|^q}{8} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{3|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{8} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

5. Summary and Concluding Remarks

In this study, Newton-type inequalities for twice-differentiable convex functions are developed using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. A new identity involving these fractional integrals is first derived and subsequently applied to establish new inequalities. These results are achieved by leveraging the convexity properties of twice-differentiable functions, along with H^q-order's

inequality and the power mean inequality. Additionally, special cases of the derived theorems are provided to illustrate the applicability of the findings.

The ideas and methods of our results relating to Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and Newton-type inequalities could open the way for further research in this field in the future. One can explore further developments or extensions of our findings by utilizing alternative fractional integral operators or convex function classes. Finally, quantum calculus can be used to obtain many Newton-type inequalities for different function classes.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The authors of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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